

Synthesis and Biocidal Activity of some Substituted Pyrazolines and Pyrimidines

C. S. ANDOTRA^{*†}, JATINDER KHAJURIA[‡], G. B. SINGH[‡] and SURJEET SINGH[‡]

^{*}Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 001

[†]Department of Pharmacology, Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu

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In continuation to our earlier work¹ on the synthesis of 5-membered heterocyclic compounds which were found to possess multifarious biological activities, we report here the synthesis of 1-acetyl-3-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-5-substituted-phenylpyrazoline-2 (3) and 2-amino-4-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-6-substituted-phenyl pyrimidines (4) and evaluation of their biological activities. The compounds were synthesised according to reaction sequence shown in the Scheme 1. Condensation of 1a and 1b with various aromatic aldehydes in ethanol in presence of NaOH by conventional Claisen-Schmidt, reaction gave the chalcones (2a-j). The chalcones (2a-j) on treatment with 80% hydrazine hydrate in glacial acetic acid yielded the desired pyrazolines (3a-j). The same chalcones (2a-j) were reacted with guanidine carbonate in presence of alkali in ethanol to give unstable dihydropyrimidines which got dehydrogenated to yield 2-amino-4-(2,4-dialkoxyphenyl)-6-substituted-phenyl.

Resonance due to two protons attached to C₄ and one attached to C₅ of pyrazoline ring showed up in the form of three doublets of doublets, exhibiting a typical splitting pattern of ABX system of protons in the case of analogous 3,5-disubstituted-2-pyrazolines (3).

The first doublet of doublet, centred at δ 3.26, was assigned to H_A ($J_{A,B}$ 18.0 and $J_{A,X}$ 5.0 Hz *trans*). Signal due to H_B should also appear as doublet of doublet at around δ 3.86; but this signal merged in the signal of OCH₃ protons. Signal due to third proton of pyrazoline also showed up as a doublet

of doublet centred at δ 5.4 attributed to H_X (J_{Z-A} 5.0 Hz *trans*, $J_{X,B}$ 11.0 Hz *cis*). The non-equivalence of C₄-H_A and C₄-H_B may be due to the presence of chiral centre at C₅, which makes the centre diastereotropic. Presumably, the appearance of H_A, at a higher field than the diastereotropic proton H_B may be attributed to the fact that H_A, being *cis* to C₅-C₆H₅ may be lying in the shielding zone of the benzene ring.

Biocidal activity: Compounds 3a-j were tested for anti-inflammatory activity by a acute carrageenan odema test model in rats² and the percentage inhibition at 3.5 h in group of four rats at 100 mg/kg p.o. were found to be 0.0, 15.9, 25.9, 8.2, 14.1, 7.7, 10.5, 8.4, 20.4, 12.0 respectively.

Compounds 4a-j were screened for antimicrobial activity against gram-positive bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus* and gram-negative bacterium *Echerichia coli* and fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans* using agar-diffusion technique³ at 10, 100 and 1000 μ g ml⁻¹ (disc size 5 mm), employing streptomycin and mycostatin respectively, as standards. All the compounds were found to exhibit low degree of inhibition, i.e. they do not possess significant antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

All m.ps. were taken on a Buchi melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP-2000 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a 60 MHz spectrometer.

- 3,4a** : R = Me, Ar = phenyl
b : R = Me, Ar = *p*-anisyl
c : R = Me, Ar = 3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl
d : R = Me, Ar = 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl
e : R = Me, Ar = 4-ethoxy-3-methoxyphenyl
f : R = Et, Ar = phenyl
g : R = Et, Ar = *p*-anisyl
h : R = Et, Ar = 3,4-methylenedioxyphenyl
i : R = Et, Ar = 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl
j : R = Et, Ar = 4-ethoxy-3-methoxyphenyl

1-(2,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (2a): To a well-stirred and cooled solution of 2,4-dimethoxyacetophenone (0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml), was added 60% aqueous NaOH (5 ml) during a period of 20 min. The reaction mixture was stirred further for 5 h at 25°. The reaction mixture was washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (90%), m.p. 75–76°; ν_{max} 1660 (C=O) and 1610 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 3.8 (6H, s, 2 × OCH₃), ϵ .55 (2H, s, 2 × C=CH) and 9.2–8.0 (8H, m, ArH). Similarly other compounds (yields 82–90%) were prepared: **2b**, m.p., 90–92°; **c**, 130–32°; **d**, 88–91°; **e**, 132°; **g**, 87–89°; **h**, 105°; **i**, 118°; **j**, 125–27°.

1-Acetyl-3-(2,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-5-phenylpyrazole-2 (3a): Compound **2a** (0.01 mol) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid and to it was added

hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4–6 h, and the resulting mixture was poured into ice-water containing liquor ammonia. The solid separated was washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, (90%), m.p. 132–35° (Found: C, 70.46; H, 6.06; N, 8.55. C₁₉H₂₀N₂O₈ requires: C, 70.37; H, 6.17; N, 8.64%); ν_{max} 1670 (C=O) and 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 2.34 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.26 (1H, dd, H_A, J_{A,B} 18.0 and J_{A,X} 5.0 Hz), 3.52–4.6 (7H, m, H_B + 2 × OCH₃), 5.4 (1H, dd, H_X, J_{X,A} 5.0 and J_{X,B} 11.0 Hz) and 6.2–8.0 (8H, m, ArH).

Similarly other compounds were prepared: **3b**, m.p. 108–10°; **c**, 124–26°; **d**, 102–04°; **e**, 125–28°; **f**, 136–38°; **g**, 95–97°; **h**, 170–72°; **i**, 104–06°; **j**, 130–33°.

2-Amino-4-(2,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine (4a): To a refluxing mixture of the chalcone (**3a**; 0.01 mol) and guanidine carbonate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml), was added 40% aqueous NaOH (5 ml) portionwise during a period of 3 h. Refluxing was continued for 7 h. Ethanol was then distilled off and the mixture was diluted with water. The resulting solid was dried and subjected to column chromatography over silica gel as it showed to be a mixture. Elution with pure benzene gave the unreacted chalcone and with benzene-ethyl acetate mixture (20 : 1) gave the required product (40%), m.p. 114–16° (Found: C, 70.25; H, 5.60; N, 13.56. C₁₈H₁₇N₃O₂ requires: C, 70.36, H, 5.54; N, 13.68%); ν_{max} 3225, 3350 (NH) and 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 3.8 (6H, s, 2 × OCH₃), 5.4 (2H, s, NH₂) and 6.4–8.2 (9H, m, ArH).

Similarly other compounds were prepared: **4b** m.p. 120–20°; **c**, 102–04°; **d**, 85–86°; **e**, 136°; **f**, 140–42°; **g** 153–55°; **h**, 182–84°; **i**, 156°; **j**, 138–40°.

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